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Microbial Remediation Measures for Fluoride Contamination

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Abstract

Fluoride is very abundant in the Earth's crust. Its usefulness ranges from several industries, agriculture to human health. The significance and use of fluoride in plants and human bodies vary and lack established conviction. However, with concentrations higher than the permissible limit, it poses a threat to soil quality, plants, microbes, and human health. This non-metal can often originate from various sources, posing a grave danger to different ecosystems and the health of organisms. Fluorosis caused by excessive fluoride is endemic in several nations, including India. To mitigate fluoride toxicity effects, conventional methods and now more sustainable biological defluoridation methods are gaining popularity. For decontamination, plants or/microorganisms are employed to remove pollutants such as fluoride. In this review, we analyzed the microbial remediation strategies to evaluate the potential of microbes towards improving soil health and environmental sustainability.

Keywords: Fluorosis; Remediation; Toxicity; Soil health

Introduction

Fluorine is the 13th most abundant element, with an approximate avg. concentration of 0.3gkg⁻¹ in the crust of our planet (Prabhu et al., 2023). Due to its high reactivity, electronegativity, and low polarizability, fluorine strongly bonds with other elements or exists as the fluoride ion. Groundwater, generally free from pathogens, can become contaminated with fluoride due to geological factors, water-rock interactions, and human activities, with fluoride concentrations influenced by recharge water composition, soil-water interactions, and aquifer reactivity (Krishnan and Asaithambi, 2024). In soils, fluoride is largely insoluble, with over 90% bound to soil particles, and its movement depends on factors like pH, soil type, and salinity, and its concentrations are estimated at 330 mg/kg in soil, with levels ranging from 100 to 1300 mg/kg in rocks, 625 mg/kg in the Earth's crust, 0.9 to 1.4 mg/L in seawater, 0.1 to 1.2 mg/L in groundwater, and 0.01 to 0.3 mg/L in surface water (Shaji et al., 2024; Prabhu et al., 2023). Fluoride can come from a variety of sources. It can be enriched in soils naturally through volcanic activities and the weathering of parent rocks, leaching from soil, together with wind-blown dust. Fluorine is a useful non-metal for industries such as pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals, etc., as well as for humans. An adequate amount of fluoride is crucial for the mineralization of bones and the development of dental enamel, as it decreases the solubility of tooth enamel, helping to prevent tooth decay over time (Dhar and Bhatnagar, 2009).

Although the effect of fluoride varies based on its concentration, species, age, growth stage, climatic conditions, geological factors, etc., fluoride can cause adverse impacts above a certain threshold. According to UNICEF, fluorosis is a global phenomenon and is endemic to at least 25 nations. Fluorosis adversely affects the structure, function, and metabolism of various body systems and organs, including the liver, muscles, heart, lungs, and reproductive systems. Deleterious consequences of high concentration of F can be seen in the plants also, such as *Trigonella*, which exhibited that fluoride toxicity adversely affected germination, biochemical, and growth parameters (Bhati et al., 2024). Prolonged exposure to environmental stresses can lead to morphological and physiological changes, including decreased enzymatic activity that causes oxidative damage that can harm lipids, proteins, and DNA in cells (Kholiya et al., 2025; Mourya et al., 2022).

Globally, over 100 countries face fluoride contamination in groundwater exceeding the World Health Organization (WHO) limit of 1.5 mg/L, with the highest impacts reported in Africa, Asia,

Europe, and the Americas, including countries like India, China, Kenya, Argentina, and Germany (Shaji et al., 2024). 200 million people across 29 countries face severe fluoride-related health risks, with nearly 60 million people in 21 states of India affected by it (Ghosh et al., 2024). In Rajasthan state, all 33 districts face fluoride contamination from natural underground weathering, with levels reaching up to 37 mg/L in some areas (Thakur et al., 2023).

Various technologies, involving sorption, ion exchange, chemical precipitation, coagulation, or biological systems, have been used to remove excessive fluoride from soil or drinking water. This review summarizes the current understanding of remediation strategies using microbes to ameliorate fluoride toxicity.

Microbial remediation

Microbial remediation is the process of eliminating pollutants and contaminants through the use of bacteria or fungi. This process occurs through three main mechanisms (Katiyar et al., 2020):

- 1) Natural attenuation - by indigenous soil microorganisms
- 2) Biostimulation - by manipulating external conditions such as nutrients, moisture, and pH
- 3) Bioaugmentation - by the use of alien microbes in situations where the native microbes prove ineffective

Aeromonas sp., *Brevibacterium* sp., *Paenibacillus* sp., and various species of *Enterobacter*, *Aeromonascaviae*, and *Pseudomonas* comfortably survived in the high fluoride concentrations (Pal et al., 2022). An abundance of *Gammaproteobacteria* within *Aspergillus* was reported in contaminated environments. Along with *Bacteroidetes*, *Bacteroidetes* these two exhibit strong adaptability and high tolerance towards fluoride (Buragohain et al., 2025). Additionally, *Bacillus halophilus* can also withstand fluoride concentrations of up to 1500 mg L⁻¹ (Buragohain et al., 2025). Several other microbes have been identified in the remediation of the fluoride-containing compounds. For instance, *Rhodococcus* sp. FP1 degrades 2-Fluorophenol, *Sphingomonas* sp. removes 3-Fluorobenzoate, *Flavobacterium* removes Fluorobenzene, while *Arthrobacter* sp., *Gordonia* sp. SH2 and *Pseudomonas* spp. target 4-fluorocinnamic acid, a,a,a-Tri fluoroacetophenone, and 4-Fluorobenzyl Alcohol respectively (Ngaiza et al., 2025). Furthermore, eight fluoride-resistant bacterial isolates were obtained from water samples collected in the Dindigul district of South India, with their resistance varying from 200 to 300 mM NaF (Chellaiah et al., 2021).

Temperature is the most prominent factor for the microbial fluoride remediation process among all, due to its direct implication in the microbial growth (Ngaiza et al., 2025). Different microbes utilized in previous studies, along with their efficacy (subject to variation in temperature, initial concentration, and duration of treatment), are presented in Table 1.

These microbes degrade the contaminants and harness them as raw materials for energy and reproduction. For this, microbes have evolved miscellaneous strategies to evade the disruption of cell machinery caused by fluoride. These strategies, for instance, are transport across the cell membrane, biosorption to the cell walls and trapping in extracellular capsules, complex formation and redox reactions, mineralization, uptake and accumulation, extracellular precipitation, and enzymatic transformation (Hussein et al., 2003). To overcome the limitation of the slow pace of phytoremediation, plants can be inoculated with plant-growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) and fungi that accelerate the contaminant removal process and make the process more reliable (Isingoma et al., 2025).

The bacterial cell wall acts as the primary defence mechanism, which prevents pollutants from entering the cell and leading to their deposition on the cell surface or within the wall structure itself. The bacterial cell wall, containing amines, sulphhydryls, carboxylates, and phosphates, binds fluoride ions, effectively reducing excessive fluoride concentrations (Katiyar et al., 2020). According to Hamilton (1990), fluoride inhibits intracellular metabolism through the influx of HF, which dissociates into H⁺ and F⁻ ions in the alkaline cytoplasm. These ions disrupt F-ATPase and enolase activity, impairing glycolysis and bacterial acid tolerance. In fluoride-resistant bacteria, however, these enzymes are thought to undergo mutations (Van Loveren et al., 2008). The "crcB" gene, responsible for the fluoride ion transporter, also bestows resistance to fluoride; it was amplified from the resistant bacteria using gene-specific PCR and subsequently used in bioremediation (Isingoma et al., 2025). Furthermore, Inoculation of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was reported to increased activity of antioxidant enzymes, for instance, superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and ascorbate oxidase (APX), which act against free radicals and also enhance activity of

urease, phosphatase, dehydrogenase, nitrate reductase, and cellulose etc., it can be utilised to promote soil health and growth of *Oryza sativa* L. in conditions of fluoride stress (Buragohain et al., 2025). PGPR can also adsorb fluoride ions on their cell walls by means of electrostatic interactions and secrete exopolysaccharides, siderophores, pigments, and volatile compounds that decrease available fluoride to plants. They also release phytohormones to mitigate fluoride toxicity and promote precipitation with Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and Al^{3+} , enabling biosorption, bioaccumulation, and detoxification, which can be more effective with phytoremediation (Singh et al., 2025).

Table 1. Use of microbes in fluoride remediation and their efficacy

Microbe	Type of organism	Fluoride removal	References
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	Bacteria	97%	Thesai et al. (2021)
<i>Shewanella putrefaciens</i> (MTCC 8104)	Bacteria	93.7 %	Dwivedi et al. (2017)
<i>Aspergillus niger</i> (MF431834)	Fungi	92%	Annadurai et al. (2023)
Immobilized cells of <i>Staphylococcus lentus</i>	Bacteria	92 %	Mukherjee et al. (2018)
<i>Aspergillus niger</i> (FS18)	Fungi	89%	Annadurai et al. (2019)
<i>Bacillus flexus</i> (PN4)	Bacteria	86%	Thesai et al. (2020)
Dead cells of <i>Staphylococcus lentus</i> (KX941098)	Bacteria	85.03 %	Mukherjee et al. (2018)
<i>Providencia vermicola</i> (KX926492)	Bacteria	82 %	Mukherjee et al. (2017b)
<i>Acinetobacter</i> sp.(H12)	Bacteria	81.91 %	Su et al. (2020)
<i>Paenibacillus</i> sp.	Bacteria	76.7%	Sharma et al. (2019)
<i>Brevibacterium</i> sp.	Bacteria	73.4%	Sharma et al. (2019)
<i>Bacillus megaterium</i> (JF273850)	Bacteria	70%	Pal et al. (2022)
<i>Aeromonas</i> sp.	Bacteria	68.7%	Sharma et al. (2019)
<i>Bacillus flexus</i> (NM25)	Bacteria	67.45 %	Pal et al. (2014)
<i>Starria zimbabweensis</i>	Blue-green algae/ cyanobacteria	66.6 %	Biswas et al. (2018)
<i>Acinetobacter</i> sp. (GU566361)	Bacteria	57.3 %	Shanker et al. (2020)
<i>Exiguobacterium indicum</i> (MLN15)	Bacteria	53.50%	Let et al. (2023)
<i>Bacillus australimaris</i> (NH71_1 ^T)	Bacteria	38.2%	Thirumala et al. (2022)
<i>Acinetobacter</i> sp. (RH5)	Bacteria	25.1 %	Mukherjee et al. (2017a)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Bacteria	22.7 %	Chouhan et al. (2012)
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> (FT1)	Bacteria	21.91 %	Banerjee et al. (2016)
<i>Bacillus marisflavi</i> (FT2)	Bacteria	20.54 %	
<i>Aspergillus penicillioides</i>	Fungi	0.0014%	Prajapat et al. (2010)

Bacteria can develop fluoride resistance, either transiently through plasmid transfer or phenotypic adaptation, or stably via chromosomal mutations, lasting up to 50 generations (Liao et al., 2017). Through conjugation, as seen in *Pseudomonas putida* with hybrid plasmids for elimination of octane, salicylate, naphthalene, and camphor, and transformation, for degrading trichloroethylene (TCE) and polychlorinated biphenyls (Ngaiza et al., 2025). Riboswitches, which are mostly metabolite-binding RNA structures found in bacterial mRNAs to regulate gene expression. Baker et al. (2012) identified fluoride-sensing riboswitches that regulate protein expression to mitigate fluoride toxicity by activating genes for fluoride transporters, with enhanced expression observed in *Escherichia coli* grown in fluoride-enriched media. Instances of this novel riboswitch, referred to as *crcB* motif RNA, have been found in various bacterial and archaeal species, as well as homologs of the associated genes in fungi, plants, and other eukaryotes, though not in humans (Breaker, 2012). *Streptococcus* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., *Bacillus* sp., and *Acinetobacter* sp. survive in high fluoride environments due to these fluoride-specific riboswitches, and both prokaryotes (Fluc) and fungi (FEX) have fluoride-specific ion transporters that export fluoride (Singh et al., 2023). Likewise, Liao et al. (2016) demonstrated through gene regulation studies that a single nucleotide modification in the promoter region (*mutp*) can greatly enhance the expression of fluoride antiporter genes *perA* and *perB*, enabling fluoride tolerance in *Streptococcus mutans*.

Fungi, known for their ecological and metabolic diversity, break down contaminants and absorb nutrients through extended mycelium penetration or extracellular digestion. Ramanaiah et al. (2007) found that dried and crushed *Pleurotus* sp. fungi could remove over 50% of fluoride. Annadurai et al. (2019) reported an adsorption efficiency of 89% for dead fungal biomass in a column experiment. Adsorption of fluoride is spontaneous, endothermic, and an efficient process

performed by fungi, which is higher in alkaline solutions, and this fungal biosorbent can be easily disposed of (Buragohain et al., 2025).

Different strategies employed by fungi against contaminants (Buragohain et al., 2025; Singh et al., 2025) are shown in Figure 1 as follows.

Fig. 1. Fungal strategies against fluoride and their outcomes

Additionally, *Aspergillus penicillioides* and *Mucor racemosus* proved more effective in removing fluoride following Ca^{+2} application. Anions such as fluoride are difficult to get rid of, as the cell surface of microbes is also negatively charged; cations like Ca seem to facilitate the removal of fluoride (Buragohain et al., 2025). *Aspergillus* sp. and *Rhizopus* sp. are also identified as agents of removal of NaF (Ngaiza et al., 2025).

Algae can also serve as cost-effective biosorbents due to alginate-rich cell walls with carboxylic groups that bind metals, form gels, and enhance biosorption, while cyanobacteria offer additional benefits through extracellular mucilage, high binding affinity, and simple nutrient requirements. Dried biomass of algae like *Dunaliella*, *Spirulina*, *Anabaena*, *Nostoc*, has shown strong potential for heavy metal removal, and algae like *Spirogyra* (IO₁, IO₂) and *Ulva fasciata*, for fluoride removal from wastewater (Mukherjee et al., 2017a). Likewise, a blue-green alga, *Phormidium* sp., was able to extract fluoride, actively participating as a biosorbent via forming active sites to accelerate the process (Ngaiza et al., 2025).

All these conventional approaches are associated with some or other challenges that limit their widespread use. Therefore, instead of relying on a single technique, integrated approaches are making strides to enhance the efficiency of fluoride decontamination. Microbial cell-based adsorbents offer a larger surface area and advantages such as being eco-friendly, cost-effective, easily available, and generating minimal sludge. In the simultaneous adsorption and bioaccumulation (SABA) process, using *Ficus religiosa* leaves and *Citrus limetta* peels as adsorbents along with *Shewanella putrefaciens* bacteria, fluoride levels were reduced from 20 ppm to below 1.5 ppm. This process demonstrated the highest fluoride removal capacity, with bioaccumulation in the bulk phase and adsorption as key mechanisms (Dwivedi et al., 2017). Similarly, Mohammad and Kumar (2019) compared fluoride removal via adsorption and SABA using sweet lemon peel and immobilized *Actinobacter*. The immobilization of microbes blocked active sites on the peel, with fluoride removal mainly occurring through bioaccumulation, making the process slower but efficient.

Genetically modified bacteria also exhibit higher bioremediation potential than natural strains, although robust application involves ecological, biotechnological, and biochemical understanding. It is also required to know the pollutant fate prediction, as the most adaptable species is favoured by the competition (Ngaiza et al., 2025). A fluoride export gene (CsFEX) was newly found and isolated from *Camellia sinensis*. The growth of CsFEX-overexpressing *E. coli* was enhanced with lower fluoride content under fluoride treatment compared to the control (Zhu et al., 2019). Synthetic microbial communities can also be built by cultivating and engineering interactions between species, and through synthetic biology, gene modification, and cooperation engineering, enhancing sustainability, cellular activity, and bioremediation efficacy under various polluted surroundings (Ngaiza et al., 2025).

Conclusion and Future Perspective

Globally, nations are putting enormous efforts into strengthening their respective economies and industries at a rapid pace. While fulfilling developmental aspirations in a non-sustainable way, the quality of air, water, and soil is compromised. On similar lines, fluoride pollution in recent times has

become a mundane reality. Fluoride affects various biological species by interrupting cell machinery and other metabolic activities. Further studies are required to validate cellular or biochemical responses under conditions of fluoride toxicity. Any approach used to treat contamination must not contribute to any other kind of pollution, which can be much harder to treat in the long run. Genetic engineering to enhance microbial resistance against fluoride and other harmful substances in soil also offers a promising solution to environmental challenges and deserves further exploration. Continual evaluation and monitoring of water sources, access to safe drinking water with essential nutrition supplements, and affordable and equitable healthcare infrastructure could potentially undo the negative effects on people's health. Mitigation of this crisis, work on the environmental front, further research, and implementation of those on the ground are a necessity. By minimizing the sources of pollution and reversing the trends in climate-driven calamities, we can enjoy the benefits of an ecosystem while protecting the interests of other species.

References

Annadurai ST, Arivalagan P, Sundaram R, Mariappan R and Munusamy AP (2019) Batch and column approach on biosorption of fluoride from aqueous medium using live, dead and various pretreated *Aspergillus niger* (FS18) biomass. *Surfaces and Interfaces* 15: 60–69.

Annadurai ST, Ragavendran C, Kamaraj C, Sundaram R, Periyasamy M, Rajendran M, Munusamy AP, De Matos LP, and Malafaia, G (2023) Studying the effects of *Aspergillus niger* (MF431834) dead biomass on water defluoridation in batch and bed column: adsorption kinetics, characterization, genotoxicity studies. *Journal of Water Process Engineering* 55: 104141.

Baker JL, Sudarsan N, Weinberg Z, Roth A, Stockbridge RB and Breaker RR (2012) Widespread genetic switches and toxicity resistance proteins for fluoride. *Science* 335(6065): 233–235.

Banerjee G, Sengupta A, Roy T, Banerjee PP, Chattopadhyay A and Ray AK (2016) Isolation and characterization of fluoride resistant bacterial strains from fluoride endemic areas of West Bengal, India: assessment of their fluoride absorption efficiency. *Fluoride* 49(4): 429–440.

Bhati J, Vijayvergia R and Kumar A (2024) Growth attributes and pigmentation of fenugreek under fluoride toxicity. *Journal of Stress Physiology & Biochemistry* 20(1): 46–56.

Biswas G, Thakurta SG, Chakrabarty J, Adhikari K and Dutta S (2018) Evaluation of fluoride bioremediation and production of biomolecules by living cyanobacteria under fluoride stress condition. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* 148: 26–36.

Breaker RR (2012) New insight on the response of bacteria to fluoride. *Caries Research* 46(1): 78–81

Buragohain K, Sonowal S, Gogoi A, Borah N and Nath R (2025) Nanoparticle-assisted microbial remediation as a potential approach to groundwater fluoride contamination. *3 Biotech* 15(9): 287.

Chellaiah ER, Ravi P and Uthandakalaipandian R (2021) Isolation and identification of high fluoride resistant bacteria from water samples of Dindigul district, Tamil Nadu, South India. *Current Research in Microbial Sciences* 2: 100038.

Chouhan S, Tuteja U and Flora SJS (2012) Isolation, identification and characterization of fluoride resistant bacteria: possible role in bioremediation. *Applied Biochemistry and Microbiology* 48(1): 43–50.

Dhar V and Bhatnagar M (2009) Physiology and toxicity of fluoride. *Indian Journal of Dental Research* 20(3): 350.

Dwivedi S, Mondal P and Balomajumder C (2017) Bioremoval of fluoride from synthetic water using gram-negative bacteria *Shewanella putrefaciens*. *Journal of Hazardous, Toxic, and Radioactive Waste* 21(2): 04016023.

Su JF, Wu ZZ, Huang TL, Zhang H, Li JW (2020) A new technology for simultaneous calcium–nitrate and fluoride removal in the biofilm reactor. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 399: 122846.

Ghosh A, Patra S, Bhattacharjee S and Bera B (2024) Severe magnitude of dental and skeletal fluorosis and its impact on society and environment in a part of Manbhum-Singhbhum Plateau, India. *BMC Public Health* 24(1): 1971.

- Hamilton IR (1990) Biochemical effects of fluoride on oral bacteria. *Journal of Dental Research* 69(2_suppl): 660–667.
- Hussein H, Farag S and Moawad H (2003) Isolation and characterization of *Pseudomonas* resistant to heavy metals contaminants. *Arab Journal of Biotechnology* 7: 13–22.
- Isingoma CL, Talukdar A, Chakraborty S and Bhattacharya S (2025) Bioremediation of fluoride: potential of bacteria, plants, and plant-microbe interactions in fluoride removal from the environment. *Geomicrobiology Journal* 1–21.
- Katiyar P, Pandey N and Sahu KK (2020) Biological approaches of fluoride remediation: potential for environmental clean-up. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 27(12): 13044–13055.
- Kholiya N, Bhati J and Kumar A (2025) Proline mediated improvement in cluster bean resilience: unrevealing growth, physiological and biochemical attributes against chromium. *Vegetos* 1–12.
- Krishnan V and Asaithambi M (2024) Hydro-meteorological aspects of soil fluorides in semi-arid soils using microwave remote sensing. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 196(7): 669.
- Let M, Majhi K and Bandopadhyay R (2023) Defluoridation efficiency of a novel fluoride-resistant *Exiguobacterium indicum* MLN15. *National Academy Science Letters* 46(6): 511–515.
- Liao Y, Brandt BW, Li J, Crielaard W, Van Loveren C and Deng DM (2017) Fluoride resistance in *Streptococcus mutans*: a mini review. *Journal of Oral Microbiology* 9(1): 1344509.
- Liao Y, Brandt BW, Zhang M, Li J, Crielaard W, Van Loveren C and Deng DM (2016) A single nucleotide change in the promoter mutp enhances fluoride resistance of *Streptococcus mutans*. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* 60(12): 7509–7512.
- Mohammad A and Kumar S (2019) Adsorptive and bio removal of fluoride from synthetic waste water by using *Actinobacter* immobilized on the surface of sweet lemon peel. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology* 8(06): 132–137.
- Mourya SK, Mohil P, and Kumar A (2022) Abiotic stress-induced changes in antioxidative system and secondary metabolites production in *Andrographis paniculata*. *Journal of Stress Physiology & Biochemistry* 18(3): 69–83.
- Mukherjee S, Mondal M, Banerjee S and Halder G (2017a) Elucidation of the sorptive uptake of fluoride by Ca²⁺-treated and untreated algal biomass of *Nostoc* sp. (BTA394): isotherm, kinetics, thermodynamics and safe disposal. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection* 107: 334–345.
- Mukherjee S, Sahu P and Halder G (2017b) Microbial remediation of fluoride-contaminated water via a novel bacterium *Providencia vermicola* (KX926492). *Journal of Environmental Management* 204: 413–423.
- Mukherjee S, Sahu P and Halder G (2018) Comparative assessment of the fluoride removal capability of immobilized and dead cells of *Staphylococcus lentus* (KX941098) isolated from contaminated groundwater. *Environmental Progress & Sustainable Energy* 37(5): 1573–1586.
- Ngaiza VV, Nungula EZ, Chappa LR, Mwadalu R, Nyambele KA, Shankar T, Ranjan S, Sow S, Uddin S, Gitari HI (2025) Biotechnological approaches to fluoride remediation. In *Fluorides in Drinking Water: Source, Issue, and Mitigation Strategies* (pp. 163–188). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Pal KC, Mondal NK, Chatterjee S, Ghosh TS and Datta JK (2014) Characterization of fluoride-tolerant halophilic *Bacillus flexus* NM25 (HQ875778) isolated from fluoride-affected soil in Birbhum District, West Bengal, India. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 186(2): 699–709.
- Pal KC, Mukhopadhyay P, Chatterjee S and Mondal NK (2022) A study on fluoride bioremediation via a novel bacterium *Bacillus megaterium* (JF273850) isolated from agricultural soil. *Journal of Earth System Science* 131(3): 183.
- Prabhu SM, Yusuf M, Ahn Y, Park HB, Choi J, Amin MA, Yadav KK, Jeon BH (2023) Fluoride occurrence in environment, regulations, and remediation methods for soil: a comprehensive review. *Chemosphere* 324: 138334.

Prajapat R, Bhatnagar A, Gaur RK and Bajpai V (2010) Fluoride removal from water by sorbing on plant and fungal biomass. *International Journal of Biological Technology* 1(1): 43–46.

Ramanaiah SV, Mohan SV and Sarma PN (2007) Adsorptive removal of fluoride from aqueous phase using waste fungus (*Pleurotus ostreatus* 1804) biosorbent: kinetics evaluation. *Ecological Engineering* 31(1): 47–56.

Shaji E, Sarath KV, Santosh M, Krishnaprasad PK, Arya BK and Babu MS (2024) Fluoride contamination in groundwater: a global review of the status, processes, challenges, and remedial measures. *Geoscience Frontiers* 15(2): 101734.

Shanker AS, Srinivasulu D and Pindi PK (2020) A study on bioremediation of fluoride-contaminated water via a novel bacterium *Acinetobacter* sp. (GU566361) isolated from potable water. *Results in Chemistry* 2: 100070.

Sharma S, Upadhyay D, Singh B, Shrivastava D and Kulshreshtha N M (2019) Defluoridation of water using autochthonous bacterial isolates. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 191(12): 781.

Singh A, Sharma A, Agrawal M and Sundaram S (2025) Fluoride: toxicity, mechanism and role of bioremediation in detoxification. *Current Microbiology* 82(8): 1–17.

Singh A, Yadav VK, Gautam H, Rathod L, Chundawat RS, Singh G, Verma RK, Sahoo DK, Patel A (2023) The role of plant growth promoting rhizobacteria in strengthening plant resistance to fluoride toxicity: a review. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 14: 1271034.

Thakur B, Loganathan VA, Sharma A, Sharma RK and Parker A (2023) Release of geogenic fluoride from contaminated soils of Rajasthan, India: experiments and geochemical modeling. *Water Security* 19: 100140.

Thesai AS, Nagarajan G, Rajakumar S, Pugazhendhi A and Ayyasamy PM (2021) Bioaccumulation of fluoride from aqueous system and genotoxicity study on *Allium cepa* using *Bacillus licheniformis*. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 407: 124367.

Thesai AS, Rajakumar S and Ayyasamy PM (2020) Removal of fluoride in aqueous medium under the optimum conditions through intracellular accumulation in *Bacillus flexus* (PN4). *Environmental Technology* 41(9): 1185–1198

Thirumala M, Krishna ES, Priya PS and Reddy SV (2022) Characterization of a novel fluoride resistant bacterial isolate and its capability of fluoride bioremediation. *AIMS Microbiology* 8(4): 470–483.

Van Loveren C, Hoogenkamp MA, Deng DM and Ten Cate JT (2008) Effects of different kinds of fluorides on enolase and ATPase activity of a fluoride-sensitive and fluoride-resistant *Streptococcus mutans* strain. *Caries Research* 42(6): 429–434.

Zhu J, Xing A, Wu Z, Tao J, Ma Y, Wen B, Zhu X, Fang W, Wang Y (2019) CsFEX, a fluoride export protein gene from *Camellia sinensis*, alleviates fluoride toxicity in transgenic *Escherichia coli* and *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 67(21): 5997–6006.

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